

NOTIONES - interacting network of intelligence and security practitioners with industry and academia actors

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1 Network of security and intelligence practitioners

NOTIONES is an EU-funded project that aims to establish an interacting network of security and intelligence practitioners with industry and academia actors to promote innovation and collaboration in the field of security research. The project brings together a diverse group of experts from various sectors to develop innovative solutions to emerging security threats.

The NOTIONES project recognizes that traditional security approaches are no longer adequate to address the complex and rapidly evolving nature of security threats. The project therefore seeks to promote a more collaborative and interdisciplinary approach to security research, involving experts from academia, industry, and security and intelligence agencies.

One of the key objectives of NOTIONES is to foster innovation in security research. This is achieved through a variety of activities, including research monitoring, technology scouting, and the development of innovative tools and methodologies for security practitioners. The project also provides a platform for knowledge sharing and collaboration, allowing participants to exchange ideas and best practices and to develop new approaches to security challenges.

Another important aspect of NOTIONES is its focus on promoting ethical and legal standards in security research. The project aims to ensure that all research and development activities are conducted in accordance with ethical and legal principles, and that the resulting technologies and methodologies are designed with privacy and human rights considerations in mind.

Through its various activities and initiatives, NOTIONES is helping to shape the future of security research by promoting collaboration, innovation, and ethical standards. The project aligns with the EU's broader objectives of promoting innovation, competitiveness, and security across Europe. Through its engagement with industry and academia actors, NOTIONES is helping to drive forward the EU's innovation agenda and to position Europe as a leader in the field of security research. The project has already made significant contributions to the field, and its

ongoing efforts are likely to have a major impact on the development of new approaches to security challenges in the years to come.

In conclusion, the NOTIONES project is an important initiative that is helping to bridge the gap between security and intelligence practitioners, industry actors, and academia, in order to develop innovative solutions to emerging security threats. By promoting collaboration, innovation, and ethical standards, NOTIONES is helping to shape the future of security research and ensure that our societies remain safe and secure in the face of ever-evolving security challenges.

Figure 1. Ecosystem of security and intelligence practitioners.

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